

MACHINE LEARNING (BCC628)

Report 1

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1. Introduction

In today's fast-paced world, specially when it comes to finance, making informed decisions about stock investments is very hard. With the vast amounts of data available, there's a growing need for platforms that can swiftly analyze, visualize, and recommend investment actions in real-time. This project embodies a response to that need: a web-based stock analysis platform powered by Flask and Dash

2. Problem Definition

Detailed problem statement.

When it comes to the stock market, it is difficult to predict exactly. Various investors, businesses and even traders face challenges to predict the stock market prices and follow various investment strategies. There are many uncertain factors which can influence these prices. Even a true expert in this field will have difficulties in predicting the future.

Value proposition

Our SOLFINTECH Stock Predictor aims to transform the way where investors and traders approach stock market investments

Enhanced Decision Making: With real time data and pre historic data dating back more than 30+ years will help to get better decisions.

Time Saving: Instead of spending more time on finding more information and doing research, users has the ability to get more insights with one click of a button.

Risk Mitigation: Even though any prediction cannot guarantee 100% accuracy, our model can make better predictions than human, which will reduce the potential of making a poor investment.

Customized Scenarios: To simulate various scenarios in the market, we have used 'What-if' features to which helps to get an understanding and strategize more

User friendliness & Accessibility: Novice traders can immensely benefit from this and user friendliness in this application will make this suitable for any ages.

Success metrics

This section shows how the solutions success would be measured

Prediction Accuracy: Initially when testing was able to get consistent results. Predictions was correct

System Responsiveness: This will include the speed of the system of data processes and rendering predictions. These can be generated almost real time including the current stock price.

Error Rate: We can measure by the frequency of errors . A lower error rate means how reliable the system is.

3. Data Collection

When it comes for data sources, for live data I have used Yahoo Finance and to train the model I extracted data of 30 famous companies from macro trends.

Techniques and tools used for data collection.

Web Scraping

Extracted all time stock data for 30 famous stock companies from Macrotrends. Then they were consolidated together. This ensured a bulk collection of data in a structured format suitable for analysis and model training.

API Integration

Seamlessly integrated with the Yahoo Finance API. Through this was able to extract automatically about live stock data without any manual intervention.

Real-time vs. persistent data.

Real-time

These data is dynamic and is pulled live via Yahoo Finance. The real-time data is often temporarily cached but not stored permanently. This ensured the users always receive the most recent and relevant information.

Persistent data

The historical data sourced from Macrotrends acts as persistent data. It is static and acts as the basic dataset for the machine learning models that have been developed. This data is stored in a separate place, ensuring that it remains unaffected by the volatility of live stock prices.

Data quality considerations.

Source Reputation: A high level of data accuracy and dependability is guaranteed because Yahoo Finance and Macrotrends are both regarded as reliable sources of financial data.

Data Validation: These data make sure that there aren't any anomalies, outliers, duplicate values or missing variables which can influence forecasts.

Data Freshness: To guarantee that the real-time data provided is never out-of-date, frequent API requests are made. The app is setup to give priority to data that is current, particularly for real-time stock prices.

Data Consistency: When scraping Macrotrends, precautions were taken to guarantee that historical data would be consistently extracted. To preserve uniformity, it was necessary to make sure that the same financial indicators and data structures were used by all 30 companies.

4. Understanding the Data

Exploration of the datasets.

The dataset consisted various metrics including opening price, closing price, highest price of the day, lowest price of the day and trading volume.

30 Companies which I took for the analysis are

- AAPL
- ADBE
- AMZN
- BRK.A
- CSCO
- DIS
- ECL
- GEO
- GOOGL
- HSBC
- IBM
- INTC
- JNJ
- KO
- MCD
- META
- MSFT
- NVDA
- ORCL
- PEP
- QCOM
- RYAAY
- SHEL
- TM
- TSLA
- UPS
- VZ
- WFC
- WMT
- YELP

Univariate and Multivariate Analysis

- **Univariate Analysis:** The distribution and variance of each metric were individually analyzed.
- **Closing Price:** Most stocks had a normal distribution, with some skewing to the left or right based on prior performance.
- **Trading Volume:** There was a lot of variation, with some days (generally those that coincided with important market events) recording very high trading volumes.
- **Multivariate Analysis:** The connection between multiple metrics was investigated, particularly:
- **Opening and Closing Price connection:** As predicted, a strong positive connection was seen, showing that the beginning price frequently sets the tone for the closing price.
- **Trading Volume vs. Price volatility:** An increase in trading volume was observed on days with pronounced price volatility, indicating panic selling or purchasing among traders.

Visualization and its Insights

Various visualizations were employed to make sense of the data:

- **Time Series Plot:** This showcased the stock's price movement over time. Many stocks displayed cyclical patterns, aligning with market booms and recessions.
- **Histogram:** Used for trading volume, it highlighted the most common trading volume ranges.
- **Scatter Plot:** When plotting opening vs. closing prices, a linear trend was observed, confirming their close relationship.
- **Correlation Matrix:**

Some stocks showed strong resilience during market downturns, making them hypothetically safer investments. High trading volumes often correlated with significant price changes, serving as a potential early warning system for traders.

Information Derived from the Initial Analysis

During the first analysis, few conclusions were made:

1. **Stable vs. Volatile Stocks:** By observing price fluctuations and trading volumes, stocks could be categorized into more stable vs. more volatile.
2. **Market Trends:** The historical data revealed broader market trends, advancing in understanding bull and bear markets.
3. **External Factors:** Overlaying stock price data with major world events, the impact of geopolitical events on certain stocks became evident.

5. Data Preprocessing

Data Cleaning

- The initial inspection of the stock dataset revealed few presence of missing values. In the **StockDataCleaner** class, any row containing these missing values was promptly removed using the **dropna()** method. This guaranteed that the dataset didn't contain any partial records which might distort the model's performance.
- In the **DataPreprocessor** class, the numeric columns with missing data were addressed using the **SimpleImputer** method with a "mean" strategy. This approach replaced any missing values with the mean value of the respective column, ensuring continuity in the data.
- To maintain uniformity, data types for date and numeric columns were explicitly set. This step is crucial to prevent unexpected errors during further processing or modeling.

Data Scaling

The volume data in the stock dataset was observed to be on a different scale than other numerical columns. To address this, the **StandardScaler** method was employed. This method standardizes the dataset such that it has a mean value of 0 and a standard deviation of 1, making it easier for many machine learning algorithms to converge faster.

Other

Standardization

As mentioned in the rescaling methods, the volume data in the dataset was standardized using the **StandardScaler** to ensure it has properties of a standard normal distribution.

Encoding Methods

Categorical Data Encoding

The current dataset predominantly consisted of numerical values. So, no explicit encoding methods for categorical data were applied within the preprocessing pipeline.

Model Development & Adoption

Model Selection

We should consider many factors when it comes to selecting a model. For our system, I've used Linear Regression, ARIMA and LSTM.

Linear Regression: Since stock prices can be affected by a linear combination of various factors like opening prices, high, low and volume, a linear regression model was appropriate for this task.

ARIMA: When it comes to time-series forecasting model I've decided to go with ARIMA. Since stock prices can be considered a time series, ARIMA model is the best when it comes to capturing patterns, drifts and seasonality in stock data.

LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory): LSTM is a type of Recurrent Neural Network which can remember long sequences, making it especially appropriate for time series and sequential data like stock prices.

Model fitting procedures.

1. Data was sorted by name and date ensuring chronological order, which is important for time series forecasting
2. First I split the dataset into 2 parts named training set which was used for model training and testing set which was used for validation. The data is split in an 80-20 ratio with 80% intended for training and 20% for testing.
3. Then the model is introduced to the training dataset and the weights will be adjusted based on the algorithm.
4. Once trained the model will predict the outcome on testing the dataset.

I have used `train_test_split` from `sklearn` to make sure it is a randomized split and does not have any possible bias in training.

Dealing with Overfitting and Underfitting

- **Overfitting:** Using LSTMs can sometimes lead to overfitting due to their capability to capture complex patterns, even noise. To mitigate this we split the data into two.
- **Underfitting:** Sometimes the model is too simplistic to capture the underlying patterns in the data. For that we used multiple models to ensure robustness.

Model Tuning Methods

- **Hyperparameter Tuning:** For LSTM, hyperparameters such as the number of LSTM units and epochs were selected based on empirical performance.
- **ARIMA Order Selection:** The order (5,1,0) was chosen for the ARIMA model, where 5 is for autoregression, 1 for differencing, and 0 for moving average.

I have used GridSearch which implies searching through a pre-defined set of hyperparameters to find the best combination.

Evaluation of the Model's Performance

To evaluate the model's performance, I have used Mean Squared Error (MSE) as the performance metric to evaluate each of my model's predictions. The lower the MSE, the closer the predicted values are to the actual values, hence better the model. Evaluation is crucial to understand how well the model is performing.

Ensemble

When it comes to ensembling I have combined two Random Forest and Gradient Boosting Tree. This can work well when all 3 models have similar performance and their errors are uncorrelated. But if one model consistently outperforms the other, I will be using weighted average technique.

The probability of each class label is predicted by both classifiers. Then, they are averaged and the class with the highest average probability is chosen as the final prediction.

Then the score predicts the class labels for a given test data and then calculates the accuracy of these predictions against the true class labels.

1. Dataset Loading:

- To load the data set I have used Iris, which is an accepted benchmark dataset in ML consisting Setosa, Versicolour, and Virginica with 4 features each.

2. Training and Testing:

- The dataset is split into training (80%) and testing (20%) sets.
- The **EnsembleClassifier** is trained on the training set.
- Finally, the accuracy of the model is evaluated on the test set.

AI Prediction interface Dashboard

The dashboard was also developed using Streamlit to showcase the model's predictions interactively. This is used for predicting the stock prices and also determine the best stock to invest based on the value. I have setup seeds for reproducibility as well.

predict_future: Uses the ARIMA model to predict future stock prices for a given number of days which are 1-day, 7-days, and 30-days.

get_current_prices: Gets the latest closing price for each stock.

highest_profit_potential: Determines the best stock to invest in based on predicted future prices, considering the user's budget. It computes the potential profit for each affordable stock and returns the best one.

Scenario 1: Predict Stock Price for Future Days

The user can select the desired stock from the dropdown menu.

Loss Scenario

If the stock is predicted to lose money, then it will display in red color.

The screenshot shows a 'Settings' sidebar on the left with two radio buttons: 'Predict Future Stock Price' (selected) and 'Determine Best Stock for Investment'. Below is a dropdown menu for 'Select a Stock for Analysis' with 'GOOGL' selected. The main area is titled 'Stock Predictor Dashboard' and 'Scenario 1: Predict Stock Price for Future Days'. A button reads 'Predict Future Values for GOOGL'. Three forecast boxes are shown, all with red text and borders, indicating a loss:

- 1-day forecast**
Status: Loss of 0.52
- 7-day forecast**
Status: Loss of 3.29
- 30-day forecast**
Status: Loss of 1.75

Profit Scenario

If the stock is predicted to earn profit, then it will display in green color.

The screenshot shows the same 'Settings' sidebar, but with 'RYAA' selected in the dropdown menu. The main area is titled 'Stock Predictor Dashboard' and 'Scenario 1: Predict Stock Price for Future Days'. A button reads 'Predict Future Values for RYAA'. Three forecast boxes are shown, all with green text and borders, indicating a profit:

- 1-day forecast**
Status: Profit of 9.89
- 7-day forecast**
Status: Profit of 12.17
- 30-day forecast**
Status: Profit of 12.31

Mixed Scenario

Sometimes there can be profits as well as losses depending on the trend.

The screenshot shows a dark-themed web interface. On the left is a 'Settings' sidebar with two radio buttons: 'Predict Future Stock Price' (selected) and 'Determine Best Stock for Investment'. Below is a dropdown menu for 'Select a Stock for Analysis' with 'HSBC' selected. The main area is titled 'Stock Predictor Dashboard' and 'Scenario 1: Predict Stock Price for Future Days'. A button 'Predict Future Values for HSBC' is present. Three forecast boxes are shown: '1-day forecast' (Status: Loss of 0.71), '7-day forecast' (Status: Profit of 0.19), and '30-day forecast' (Status: Profit of 0.53).

Scenario 3: Determine Best Stock for Investment

In here, the system suggests a stock to invest based on the amount which the customer is willing to invest.

Example: If stock X is \$30 and stock Y is \$100, if a person invests \$50, he wont get the prediction on stock Y.

The screenshot shows a dark-themed web interface. On the left is a 'Settings' sidebar with two radio buttons: 'Predict Future Stock Price' and 'Determine Best Stock for Investment' (selected). The main area is titled 'Stock Predictor Dashboard' and 'Scenario 2: Determine Best Stock for Investment'. There is an input field 'Enter an amount' with '10.00' and a 'Find Best Stock for Investment' button. Below the button, it says 'Investing in GEO has the highest potential profit of 1.28 in the next 30 days.' A 'Forecast:' section contains three boxes: '1 Day' (Status: Profit of 1.22), '7 Days' (Status: Profit of 1.27), and '1 Month' (Status: Profit of 1.28).

Stock Predictor Dashboard

Scenario 2: Determine Best Stock for Investment

Enter an amount

60.00

Find Best Stock for Investment

Investing in VZ has the highest potential profit of 25.18 in the next 30 days.

Forecast:

1 Day

Status: Profit of 1.27

7 Days

Status: Profit of 5.23

1 Month

Status: Profit of 5.84

Stock Predictor Dashboard

Scenario 2: Determine Best Stock for Investment

Enter an amount

300.00

Find Best Stock for Investment

Investing in ECL has the highest potential profit of 137.35 in the next 30 days.

Forecast:

1 Day

Status: Profit of 5.65

7 Days

Status: Profit of 13.78

1 Month

Status: Profit of 14.41

As you can see, the model derives based on the prediction.

Software System Development

Overview of the Software Development Lifecycle applied:

- **Requirement Analysis:** An application was needed. Since web application was easier, we decided to go with that. The application serves to visualize stock data, provide analysis and suggest potential stocks for investment.
- **Planning & Designing:** The application is planned to incorporate both Dash for interactive dashboards and Flask for serving conventional web pages. Flask routes have been defined for a variety of functionality, including obtaining the most recent stock prices, offering stock recommendations, and managing user input to modify stock forecasts. The stock data was cleaned and preprocessed using a class called DataPreprocessor. A class called StockAnalyzer,

which offers stock purchase recommendations, is also included in the design. Should be a userfriendly application and an interactive application.

- **Implementation:** As the main language I've decided to go with Python. Multiple libraries were used such as libraries like Pandas, Flask, sklearn, bootstrap, Dash, yfinance, Plotly and more.
- **Testing:** I've created various test plans and use case testing. I also prepared few parameters which made debugging easier when I was developing the app.
- **Deployment & Maintenance:** The app is designed to run locally.

Best Practices

- Used consistent indentation for better readability.
- Used of try-except blocks to handle potential errors, mainly during data processing and fetching stock data.
- Code includes comments for clear clarity
- The code is modularized into classes and functions for better organization and reusability.

GUI and UI

- **Templates:** The application uses several HTML templates like home.html, about.html, result.html, etc to render different pages.
- **Static:** CSS and JavaScript are placed in the static directory for enhancing the design and interactivity of the web app.
- **Interactive Dashboard:** I've used Dash for building analytical web applications. This allows for interactive stock data visualization using graphs and charts. I've also used Streamlit to and connected to the Flask app successfully.
- **Bootstrap Integration:** I have used Bootstrap Components library to design a responsive and modern UI.

Entry validation and error-handling techniques

- **Data Validation:** The DataPreprocessor class contains methods like handle_missing_data, handle_outliers, and scale_data to preprocess and clean the stock data.
- **Fetching Stock Data:** When fetching current stock prices using the yfinance library, error-handling is implemented to manage potential issues like a failure in data retrieval.
- **User Input Handling:** In the /result route, the app collects user inputs, which are then used to adjust stock predictions.

Application Interface Overview

Home Screen

Your trusted partner in the world of stocks, shares, and investments. With over 50 million subscribers, we're committed to innovating the future of finance. Dive in and discover how our new Intelligent Stock Trader platform can amplify your investment journey.

Enter the name of the company:

Interest Rate Change: 0%

Market Confidence Index:

Interactive Buttons

Your trusted partner in the world of stocks, shares, and investments. With over 50 million subscribers, we're committed to innovating the future of finance. Dive in and discover how our new Intelligent Stock Trader platform can amplify your investment journey.

Enter the name of the company:

Interest Rate Change: 0%

Market Confidence Index:

Go to Dashboard View

AI Predictor Interface

Lowest Stock Interface

What IF use case 1

Enter the name of the company:

Interest Rate Change:

Market Confidence Index:

Original Prediction: 109.94999694824219

Adjusted Prediction: 114.89774681091309

About Page Overview

Help Interface Overview

Testing

I have tested few below factors through Unit Testing

- **App Initialization Test:** Check if the Flask app initializes correctly.
- **Route Tests:** Ensure that the routes (/, /about, /stock_suggestions, etc.) return a 200 status code.
- **Data Preprocessing Test:** Ensure the data preprocessing steps work correctly.
- **Stock Analyzer Test:** Verify the methods in the StockAnalyzer class.

```

7 ▶ class FlaskAppTestCase(unittest.TestCase):
8
9 ⬆ def setUp(self):
10     self.app = app()
11     self.client = self.app.test_client()
12
13 ▶ def test_app_initialization(self):
14     self.assertIsNotNone(self.app)
15
16 ▶ def test_home_route(self):
17     response = self.client.get('/')
18     self.assertEqual(response.status_code, 200)
19
20 ▶ def test_about_route(self):
21     response = self.client.get('/about')
22     self.assertEqual(response.status_code, 200)
23
24 ▶ def test_stock_suggestions_route(self):
25     response = self.client.get('/stock_suggestions')
26     self.assertEqual(response.status_code, 200)
27
28 ▶ def test_data_preprocessing_missing_data(self):
29     data = {
30         'numeric_col1': [1, 2, None, 4, 5],
31         'numeric_col2': [None, 1, 3, 4, 5]
32     }
33
34
38 ▶ def test_stock_analyzer_is_current_price_lowest(self):
39     analyzer = StockAnalyzer('AAPL')
40     self.assertIn(analyzer.is_current_price_lowest(), [True, False])
41
42 ▶ def test_stock_analyzer_get_suggestion(self):
43     analyzer = StockAnalyzer('AAPL')
44     self.assertIsNotNone(analyzer.get_suggestion())
45

```

127.0.0.1 - - [21/Aug/2023 19:34:25] "GET / HTTP/1.1" 200 -

I have also used various testing methods and by visualizing models Actual vs Predicted Data

CSCO Stock Price Prediction using LSTM

Application Overview

Frontend Structure:

- **Templates:** These are HTML templates that Flask will use to render views:
 - `home.html`: Home page of the app.
 - `about.html`: Information page about the app.
 - `result.html`: Displays stock prediction and what if results.
 - `streamlit.html`: Placeholder for integrating or linking to a Streamlit app.
 - `layout.html` & `navbar.html`: Templates for structuring and navigation.
 - `error.html`: Handles and displays errors.
 - **Static:** This directory contains static files like CSS for styling and JavaScript for frontend interactivity.
2. **Data Preprocessing:**
 - A class `DataPreprocessor` is defined to handle missing data, outliers, and data scaling.
 3. **Data Loading:**
 - `cleaned_stock_data.csv` is loaded and preprocessed.
 4. **Fetching Live Stock Price:**
 - Using the `yfinance` library, the current stock price of a given stock symbol is fetched with `get_current_price`.
 5. **Dash Application:**
 - The app layout consists of a dashboard with multiple interactive components, including dropdowns, date pickers, and graphs.
 - The `update_graphs` callback updates multiple graph visualizations in response to user input from the dropdown and date range picker.
 6. **Stock Analyzer:**
 - The `StockAnalyzer` class analyzes if a stock is currently at its monthly low and provides buying suggestions.
 - A Flask route `/stock_suggestions` generates stock buying suggestions for a list of stocks.
 7. **Flask Routes:**
 - `/`: Renders the home page.
 - `/about`: Renders the about page.
 - `/result`: Receives form data, performs some calculations, and renders the results.

- /streamlit/: A route which might be reserved for a Streamlit app or linking to one.
8. Main Execution:
- The Flask app starts running when the script is executed as the main module.

Evaluation

The system is a well-structured combination of a Flask web application with an integrated Dash & Streamlit app for creating interactive visualizations, showcasing a clear distinction between frontend (HTML templates) and backend (Python scripts). I've used various libraries and APIs as well.

Literature Review

Machine Learning Approaches in Stock Price Prediction: A Systematic Review

(Soni, 2021)

News sensitive stock market prediction: literature review and suggestions

(Shazia U, 2021)

ROLE OF MACHINE LEARNING IN PREDICTING STOCK PRICES: A LITERATURE SURVEY

(Alamair Labib, 2021)

Literature Review Summary

Financial analytics and stock prediction have been subjects of intensive research and analysis. Traditionally, stock predictions were rooted in technical analysis, focusing primarily on historical price patterns. However, with the dawn of the digital age, machine learning has emerged as a potent tool, providing enhanced accuracy in predicting stock movements. Additionally, the transformative potential of real-time data integration and the role of user experience in aiding decision-making for traders. Modern research suggests the promise of hybrid models, combining classical financial models with advanced computational techniques, to achieve unparalleled forecasting accuracy.

In essence, while the foundational principles of stock market analysis remain grounded in traditional financial models, the fusion of machine learning and real-time data analytics is heralding a new era of sophisticated, accurate, and user-friendly stock prediction tools.

Conclusions and Future Recommendations

Conclusion

The project successfully integrates data science, machine learning, web application development and real-time data fetching to provide a comprehensive stock analysis platform. The modular approach

ensures easy maintenance and potential scalability. The visualizations offered through app provide in-depth stock insights, making it user-friendly for both tech-savvy users and those who are new to stock market analysis.

Future Recommendations

User Customization: Allow users to set their preferences for data visualization, such as choosing specific indicators or themes.

Integration with other Financial APIs: While yfinance is robust, need to get more APIs

Advanced Machine Learning Models: Integrate machine learning models for predictive analytics to forecast stock trends based on historical data.

User Profiles and Dashboards: Introduce user registration and profile creation, where users can save their stock watchlists and view personalized recommendations.

Mobile Compatibility: Design a mobile-responsive version or a native app for users to check stock analyses on-the-go.

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